

a hypersensitive response that was visible 5 DAI. Resistance response was varied: leaves showed discrete, small white patches bordered by a yellowish halo, sometimes over the entire leaf surface, or the leaf midrib became yellowish, either in discrete areas or along its length (see fig., B). In what appears to be a strong resistant response, a length of the emerging leaf was completely chlorotic below a green tip, with the leaf often folding in the chlorotic region.

This response differs markedly from the well-described susceptible reaction.

The necrosis of infected resistant tissue is rapid, whereas it is slower in the susceptible response and usually follows a secondary infection by fungi.

The response was observed in some seedlings of Bazail 65, CNL 319, Karkati 161, Rayada 16-02, Rayada 16-03, and Rayada 16-06 to Rayada 16-09. We screened 100 seedlings of Rayada 16-06 to examine interplant variation. We observed host responses (see table). Within a rice line, or between lines and cultivars, the type of response and level of susceptibility could be accurately

judged from visual symptoms. Numerical scores of susceptible symptom severity at 28 DAI were linearly related to numbers of *D. angustus*/ plant (within Rayada 16-06, correlation coefficient $r = 0.70$, $P < 0.001$; between lines and cultivars, $r = 0.74$, $P < 0.001$).

Results indicate that host variation has a strong genetic component and that single plants can be qualitatively assessed. Differences in the level of susceptibility in compatible responses depend on the reproduction rate of *D. angustus* which has an environmental component. □

Irrigated germplasm improvement—irrigated

Yield performance of some new rice hybrids in Indonesia

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We compared 7 IRRI rice hybrids and 13 Indonesian hybrids with IR64 and

Way-Seputih in yield trials during the 1990-91 wet season (WS) in Sukamandi and Kuningan. Single seedlings were transplanted at 20- × 20-cm spacing in 3- × 5-m² plots with three replications. Plots were fertilized with 135-50-50 kg NPK/ha.

IR64616 H, IR64618 H, IR64610 H, and IR62829 A/IR54 yielded more than Way-Seputih, although all the rice

hybrids yielded significantly less than best check IR64 at Sukamandi. The hybrids had lower 1,000-grain weights and less filled grains/panicle than IR64.

All test entries at Sukamandi outperformed those at Kuningan. IR64 and Way-Seputih, however, still yielded significantly more than any of the hybrids (see table). □

Grain yield, maturity, 1000-grain weight, filled grains per panicle, panicle number per hill, unfilled grains per panicle, and plant height of some rice hybrids. Sukamandi (S) and Kuningan (K), Indonesia, 1990-91 WS.

Hybrid or check	Yield (t/ha)		Maturity (d)		1000-grain weight (g)		Filled grains/panicle (no.)		Unfilled grains/panicle (no.)		Panicles/hill		Plant height (cm)	
	S	K	S	K	S	K	S	K	S	K	S	K	S	K
IR64 (check)	6.8	4.7	116	133	30.20	26.97	100	61	15	31	14	11	116	84
IR64616 H	6.3	3.0	114	132	26.57	23.80	98	47	52	64	14	12	102	81
IR64618	5.2	3.6	112	127	24.90	22.03	97	69	27	33	14	13	106	84
IR64610H	4.9	3.7	111	130	24.57	22.06	83	61	31	51	16	14	101	83
IR62829 A/IR54	4.8	4.0	116	127	26.70	23.03	78	46	50	54	15	13	107	84
Way-Seputih (check)	4.7	4.9	130	133	31.30	27.57	100	91	23	35	16	11	125	85
IR64611 H	4.6	3.9	112	129	25.73	22.90	72	57	57	47	17	12	113	84
IR62829 A/M666	4.4	4.1	116	127	26.20	23.17	86	48	61	42	20	14	104	83
IR62829 A/IR64	4.4	3.3	118	120	26.17	22.83	101	46	65	44	14	15	109	82
IR62829 A/Cimanuk	4.2	3.2	115	127	25.63	21.70	88	47	46	48	15	12	96	84
IR54752 A/M66b	4.2	2.1	120	129	28.83	25.40	139	41	44	53	15	12	135	88
V20 A/M66b	4.2	2.3	104	122	27.73	24.17	87	56	28	38	14	10	108	82
IR64617 H	3.8	-	120	-	25.83	-	77	-	74	-	14	-	117	-
V20 A/IR64	3.8	2.5	104	122	28.63	23.00	90	49	32	46	13	12	106	77
IR6461514	3.5	1.7	117	132	27.03	24.06	82	49	76	37	11	11	113	83
IR54752 A/IR54	3.5	1.8	122	129	27.67	26.17	97	50	40	67	15	12	135	92
IR54752 A/IR64	3.3	1.4	121	127	29.17	26.63	108	50	50	52	19	11	134	87
V20 A/IR54	3.3	2.0	103	122	27.70	22.53	109	68	32	36	12	12	111	83
V20 A/Cimanuk	2.6	2.0	104	122	27.90	22.80	100	52	35	40	12	11	102	77
IR54752 A/Sadang	2.6	1.2	121	127	30.20	26.20	99	44	50	84	18	11	146	87
IR54752 A/Cimanuk	2.6	1.5	120	127	29.33	25.60	110	41	45	66	18	11	135	93
IR58025 A/IR54742	2.5	3.6	130	133	31.13	26.93	118	65	68	43	17	12	134	88
LSD 0.05	1.3	0.7	3.0	2.0	1.17	0.54	31.5	16.7	22.3	15.1	4.9	1.3	7.9	3.8
CV (%)	20.1	17.1	1.7	1.2	2.61	1.37	20.6	19.6	29.9	18.8	20.6	6.6	4.2	2.8